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Combining Organic and Synthetic Fertilizers for Green Mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) Production

Author's Details:

Nanik Setyowati^{1*}, Faisal Abdullah Muharam², Entang Inorih³, Zainal Muktamar⁴, Heru Widiyono⁵, Merakati Handajarningsih⁶

^{1,3,6} Department of Crop Production, University of Bengkulu, Bengkulu, 38121, Indonesia.

² Agroecotechnology Study Program, University of Bengkulu, Bengkulu, 38121, Indonesia.

^{4,5} Department of Crop Production, University of Bengkulu, Bengkulu, 38121, Indonesia.

*Email: nsetyowati@unib.ac.id

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Abstract

Excessive usage of synthetic fertilizer will cause the degradation of soil structure (hardening) and decreasing crop yield. On the other hand, organic matter improves soil structure and stability of soil aggregates, allowing for optimal soil aeration and increased fertilizer efficiency. This research aimed to determine the best combination of cow manure and vermicompost with synthetic N for greens mustard growth and yield. The research was conducted in Rawa Makmur Village, Muara Bangkahulu District, Bengkulu City, Indonesia, using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The study consisted of 10 treatments and five replications, namely $P_0 =$ No fertilization (control), $P_1 =$ N 138 kg/ha, $P_2 =$ Cow manure 20 tons/ha, $P_3 =$ Vermicompost 15 tons/ha, $P_4 = 25\% P_2 + 75\% P_1$, $P_5 = 50\% P_2 + 50\% P_1$, $P_6 = 75\% P_2 + 25\% P_1$, $P_7 = 25\% P_3 + 75\% P_1$, $P_8 = 50\% P_3 + 50\% P_1$, $P_9 = 75\% P_3 + 25\% P_1$. The results showed that 50% cow manure + 50% urea and 75% cow manure + 25% urea are combinations for the highest growth and yield of green mustard in Ultisols.

Key words: *Brassica juncea*, fertilizer substitution, green mustard, organic farming, sustainable agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the demand for vegetables is increasing following population growth and per capita consumption. In addition, customers demand a higher quality horticulture product, such as green mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.). Mustard requires adequate and readily available nutrients for growth and development to produce high yield. Nitrogen (N) is an essential nutrient for leaf growth. According to Lakitan (2008) applying N at the proper dose will promote plant growth and metabolism, protein and carbohydrate synthesis, and plant growth and productivity. Nitrogen deficiency in plant leads to slower growth, yellowish leaves, and decreased plant productivity. Nitrogen functions as a main component of proteins, nucleic acids, chlorophyll, and various metabolic compounds in the process of photosynthesis and respiration.

According to Lingga and Marsono (2013), in the life cycle of plants, relying just on nutrients from the soil is insufficient; additional nutrients inputs, both synthetic and organic fertilizers, are required. Intensive farming practices have stimulated an increase in the use of synthetic fertilizers. Using organic materials could be an alternative to reduce the reliance on synthetic fertilizers to increasing green mustard yield. In addition to the increase in nutrient availability, the application of organic matter to the soil will improve soil structure and raise the stability of soil aggregates, allowing for optimal soil aeration and an increase in fertilizer efficiency (Hayati et al., 2012).

Organic fertilizers can partly substitute synthetic fertilizers to enhance the effectiveness of nutrient absorption from synthetic fertilizers. According to Triwulaningrum (2009), the balanced application of organic and synthetic fertilizers could be the key to optimal fertilization because each has advantages and disadvantages. Synthetic fertilizer rapidly releases nutrients in the form of ions, which are easily accessible to plants to increase plant productivity. However, excessive application of this fertilizer will lower soil pH (Wulandari et al. 2017; Wang et al., 2020) and cause the destruction of soil structure (Savci, 2012). On the other hand, organic matter in organic fertilizers can improve the soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. Application of organic fertilizer increased growth and yield of onion (Prasetyo et al. 2020), soybean (Andriani et al, 2020), tomato (Setyowati et al, 2021a; Herison et al. 2022), eggplant (Setyowati et al. 2021b), and sweet corn (Hasanudin et al. 2022),

Organic fertilizers also have disadvantages. Since organic fertilizers are bulky with a low macro and micronutrient content, they must be used in large quantities. Also, organic fertilizer slowly releases plant nutrients. According to Mukhtar et al. (2020) organic fertilizer releases phosphorous slowly at the first 2 weeks after the application, even though significantly afterward. According to Yeboah et al. (2009), combining organic and synthetic fertilizers increases plant growth because organic matter improves soil properties, leading to more available nutrients to plants.

According to Wahid et al. (2015), a combination of synthetic fertilizers and organic fertilizers resulted in higher growth and yields of mustard than using solely synthetic fertilizers or only organic fertilizers. Study by Parluhutan and Santoso (2020), applying cow dung manure at a dose of 20 tons/ha significantly increased the height, total weight, economic weight, and dry weight of mustard greens as compared to treatments with lower doses. The application of urea at a dose of 200 kg/ha produces higher mustard yields than lower doses or 250 kg/ha (Sarif et al., 2015). Combination of synthetic and organic fertilizer increased plant growth and yield of mustard (Mukhtar et al., 2016), sweet corn (Setyowati et al, 2022), Chinese water spinach (*Ipomoea reptans* Poir) (Turmudhi et al. 2022).

It is essential to apply the proper combination of synthetic and organic fertilizers. Therefore, a study is necessary to determine the appropriate combination of cow dung manure, vermicompost organic, and urea on the growth and yield of green mustard. The study aimed to determine the best combination of cow manure and vermicompost with synthetic N dosage on the growth and yield of green mustard.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study was carried out in November to March 2022 in Rawa Makmur Village, Muara Bangkahulu SubDistrict, Bengkulu City, Indonesia, at an elevation of approximately 10 meters above sea level.

The study employed a completely randomized design (CRD) consisting of 10 treatments and 5 replications. The treatments included P_0 = No fertilization (control), P_1 = N 138 kg/ha, P_2 = Cow manure 20 ton/ha, P_3 = Vermicompost 15 ton/ha, P_4 = 25% P_2 + 75% P_1 , P_5 = 50% P_2 + 50% P_1 , P_6 = 75% P_2 + 25% P_1 , P_7 = 25% P_3 + 75% P_1 , P_8 = 50% P_3 + 50% P_1 , P_9 = 75% P_3 + 25% P_1 .

A planting media was an Ultisols collected from Rawa Makmur Village. The soil was sampled from the depth of 0-20 cm, air-dried for three days before planting and sieved using a 5 mm × 5 mm (l x w) sieve. After sieving, the soil was mixed with cow dung and vermicompost according to the treatment. The soil, then, was placed in a polybag of 25 cm x 25 cm (l x w) up to 2 cm from the top surface. The mixed planting medium was incubated for three weeks to allow the organic matter decomposition.

The study used Shinta variety of green mustard seeds. The seed was soaked in water for 12 hours to sort the seeds. The selected seeds based on the criteria including those were sink, round in shape, small, blackish-brown skin color, as well as smooth and shiny surface. After being soaked in water, seeds were dried using paper towels, and sown on nursery trays. The nursery media were made up of a 1:1 mixture of topsoil and cow manure. The seedlings were transplanted to polybags after 14 days or when 2 true leaves emerged.

Cow manure and vermicompost were applied 3 weeks before transplanting. Urea application was carried out one week after transplanting (WAP). The media was watered when required to maintain the moisten media. Pest and disease were controlled by spraying pesticides on pest and disease-infested plants, and weed control was conducted at 2 WAP. After 45 days after transplanting, green mustard was harvested.

Variables observed included plant height (cm), number of leaves, leaves greenness, crop fresh weight (g), leaves fresh weight (g), root fresh weight (g), plant dry weight (g), leaves dry weight (g), root dry weight (g), and plant economic weight (g).

Data Analysis

Data were statistically analyzed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) with F-test 5%; The treatment means were compared using DMRT at 5% level.

RESULTS

The results of the analysis of variance showed that the treatment had a significant effect on all observed variables, namely plant height, number of leaves, fresh weight of plants, leaves and roots, dry weight of plants, leaves and roots, leaves greenness, and economic weight of plants (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of analysis of variance

Variables	F-calculated	Coev. Variation (%)
Plant height	17.11*	15.24
Leaves number	9.88*	17.19
Leaves greenness	7.44*	12.33
Crop fresh weight [#]	16.72*	21.76
Leaves fresh weight [#]	18.09*	19.21
Root fresh weight [#]	6.71*	23.27
Crop dry weight [#]	14.14*	16.47
Leaves dry weight [#]	17.21*	15.38
Root dry weight [#]	4.96*	21.92
Crop Economic weight [#]	10.48*	18.92

Note : * = significantly different, [#] = data transformation ($\sqrt{X + 1}$), F-table (5%) = 2.12

Green Mustard Growth

The P₆ (75% P₂ + 25% P₁) treatment yielded the tallest plants (28.15 cm) while the control produced the shortest plant height, even though it wasn't significantly different from the P₁ and P₇ treatments. The P₆ treatment produced more leaves; however, it was relatively similar to the P₅ and P₂ treatments, which yielded 11.0, 10.6, and 11.3 leaves, respectively. As with plant height, the lowest number of leaves was also produced from the control (P₀), which was not significantly different from the P₁ and P₇ treatments. The control treatment generated the lowest leaf greenness. The finding of this study indicates that applying fertilizers such as urea, cow manure, vermicompost, or a combination of the two can increase the greenness of the leaves (Table 2).

Table 2. The effect of N-synthetic and organic fertilizer on mustard plant height, leaf number, and leaf greenness.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Leaves number	Leaves greenness
P ₀	11.55 e	5.40 e	28.34 d
P ₁	12.80 de	6.80 de	38.36 c
P ₂	24.20 b	11.30 a	38.56 c
P ₃	18.15 c	8.70 bcd	43.58 abc
P ₄	18.00 c	8.90 bc	47.50 ab
P ₅	21.80 b	10.60 ab	49.62 a
P ₆	28.15 a	11.00 a	48.10 ab
P ₇	15.10 cd	6.50 e	41.46 bc
P ₈	15.55 cd	6.90 cde	38.86 c
P ₉	17.35 c	8.70 bcd	44.80 abc

Note : P₀ = control P₁ = N 138 kg/ha, P₂ = Cow manure 20 ton/ha, P₃ = Vermicompos 15 ton/ha, P₄ = 25% P₂ + 75% P₁, P₅ = 50% P₂ + 50% P₁, P₆ = 75% P₂ + 25% P₁, P₇ = 25% P₃ + 75% P₁, P₈ = 50% P₃ + 50%

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P₁, P₉ = 75% P₃ + 25% P₁. Numbers followed by different letters in the same column were significantly different on the DMRT 5% test

Treatments P₂, P₅, and P₆ produced higher plant height and leaf number than other treatments. Treatment P₅ combines 50% cow manure + 50% urea, while P₆ combines 75% cow manure + 25% urea. According to the findings of this study, fertilized plants can increase the greenness of their leaves; however, synthetic fertilizers alone cannot fully meet the needs of plant growth because plant height and leaves number between treatments P₀ and P₁ were not significantly different. As a result, the planting media influence the development of green mustard. Cow manure and vermicompost applied to various treatment combinations might improve plant height, number of leaves, and green leaves (Table 2).

Green Mustard Yield

In line with plant growth, treatments P₅ and P₆ produced higher plant fresh and dry weights and plant economic weights than other treatments. The fresh and dry weights of these plants were much higher than the control (P₀) and the treatment of synthetic urea alone (P₁) (Tables 3 and 4).

Table 3. The effect of N-synthetic and organic fertilizer on mustard on crop fresh weight, leaf fresh weight, root fresh weight and crop economic weight

Treatment	Leaves fresh weight		Crop economic weight	
	Crop fresh weight (g)	(g)	Root fresh weight (g)	(g)
P ₀	3.58 c	2.80 c	0.78 b	2.14 c
P ₁	5.78 c	4.30 c	1.48 b	3.24 c
P ₂	32.12 b	29.00 b	2.50 b	24.44 b
P ₃	17.08 b	14.68 b	2.38 b	12.56 b
P ₄	13.02 c	11.08 c	1.94 b	13.84 b
P ₅	62.08 a	50.50 a	11.58 a	41.20 a
P ₆	59.44 a	51.30 a	8.14 a	46.60 a
P ₇	5.58 c	4.46 c	1.12 b	3.12 c
P ₈	8.18 c	6.60 c	1.58 b	5.50 c
P ₉	13.70 c	12.06 c	1.64 b	8.98 c

Note : P₀ = control P₁ = N 138 kg/ha, P₂ = Cow manure 20 ton/ha, P₃ = Vermicompos 15 ton/ha, P₄ = 25% P₂ + 75% P₁, P₅ = 50% P₂ + 50% P₁, P₆ = 75% P₂ + 25% P₁, P₇ = 25% P₃ + 75% P₁, P₈ = 50% P₃ + 50% P₁, P₉ = 75% P₃ + 25% P₁. Numbers followed by different letters in the same column were significantly different on the DMRT 5% test

Table 4. The effect of N-synthetic and organic fertilizer on mustard on crop dry weight, leaf dry weight, and root dry weight.

Treatment	Crop dry weight (g)	Leaves dry weight (g)	Root dry weight (g)
P ₀	0.74 c	0.50 c	0.26 b
P ₁	0.92 c	0.62 c	0.28 b
P ₂	4.78 b	4.14 b	0.62 b
P ₃	2.98 b	2.44 b	0.56 b
P ₄	1.98 c	1.60 c	0.36 b
P ₅	9.54 a	7.60 a	1.90 a
P ₆	8.72 a	7.32 a	1.40 a
P ₇	0.98 c	0.66 c	0.32 b
P ₈	1.30 c	0.98 c	0.32 b
P ₉	2.16 c	1.74 c	0.42 b

Note : P₀ = control P₁ = N 138 kg/ha, P₂ = Cow manure 20 ton/ha, P₃ = Vermicompos 15 ton/ha, P₄ = 25% P₂ + 75% P₁, P₅ = 50% P₂ + 50% P₁, P₆ = 75% P₂ + 25% P₁, P₇ = 25% P₃ + 75% P₁, P₈ = 50% P₃ + 50% P₁, P₉ = 75% P₃ + 25% P₁. Numbers followed by different letters in the same column were significantly different on the DMRT 5% test

Manure + urea (P₄, P₅, and P₆) yielded higher plant height, number of leaves, and greenness than vermicompost + urea (P₇, P₈, and P₉). A similar pattern was observed in crop fresh, dry, and economic weights, where treatments P₅ and P₆ having higher plant weights than treatments P₇, P₈, and P₉. The results also revealed that the combination of vermicompost and urea resulted in significantly higher than those fertilized using synthetic urea fertilizer alone (P₁). Plants fertilized with a combination of vermicompost + urea (P₇, P₈, and P₉) tended to produce heavier plants than those fertilized only with synthetic N fertilizer (P₁). As a result, the role of organic matter in plant growth and yield is essential.

DISCUSSION

Unfertilized green mustard grew slower than those fertilized with synthetic N and organic fertilizer (cow manure and vermicompost) or the combination. Plants require macro and micronutrients to grow and develop. Nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and C, H, and O are the macronutrients. While secondary nutrients include calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and sulfur (S), and micronutrients include iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), boron (B), bolybdenum (Mo) and chlore (Cl) (Chad, 2014)

Nitrogen is a macronutrient essential for plants, particularly those harvested for their leaves, such as green mustard. Nitrogen promotes vegetative growth in plants, notably roots, stems, and leaves. Likewise, N is crucial to forming chlorophyll, which is essential in the photosynthetic process. Nitrogen also synthesizes proteins, lipids, and other chemical compounds. Nitrogen deficiency will exhibit symptoms such as slow plant development, thin and stunted, and yellowish leaves (Taiz and Zeiger, 2002). In this study, unfertilized green mustard was shorter, fewer leaves, lower leaves greenness, and lower plant weight than those that were fertilized, indicating lower absorption of N.

Nitrogen deficiency causes abnormal growth of plants (Triadiati et al., 2012) because plants do not uptake adequate nutrients for their growth and development (Rahardjo and Pribadi, 2010). The application of Singapore daisy compost considerably improves the chemical properties of Ultisols by increasing total soil nitrogen (Muktamar et al. 2022). Other study showed that the application of vermicompost to the soil increased available nitrate and soil pH (Muktamar et al. 2022b).

Table 2, 3 and 4 demonstrate that the grow and yield of green mustard fertilized with synthetic fertilizer N (P₁) were not significantly different from those of the control (P₀). In contrast, those fertilized with cow manure + N had higher growth and yields. The application of cow manure + N resulted in higher growth and yields than the application of vermicompost + N. This result is associated with that organic matter improves soil physical, chemical, and biological qualities. Our findings suggest that the application of organic matter to Ultisols is necessary to enhance plant growth and yield. Improvement of the fertility due to the addition of organic matter will provide adequate nutrients for plant growth and yield.

Organic materials are resources derived from organisms such as plants, animals, and microbes. Plant roots, stems, branches, leaves, and fruit are primary sources of organic matter (Allison, 1973). Organic matter significantly increases the soil ability to support plant growth and yield. Organic matter plays a role in increasing soil fertility, improving soil structure, increasing soil water retention, increasing soil pores, and improving soil microbial growth media. On the other hand, soil with a low organic matter content indicates that the soil's potential to support plant productivity is likewise limited (Chad, 2014). Since Ultisols have low organic matter content, addition of this material is necessary to support plant growth. Moreover, synthetic N fertilizer stimulates plant growth, particularly during the vegetative phase; nevertheless, N is quickly leached, necessitating adding organic matter, which can enhance water-holding capacity and soil cations (Meade et al., 2011).

The P₆ treatment (75% cow manure + 25% N) yielded the highest plant fresh weight, however it was still lower than the yield potential of the Shinta variety of green mustard, which reached 500 g/plant. This might be related to the fertility of the soil used in this study. This study used Ultisol as growth media with low soil fertility and acidic. In this experiment, the Ultisols had pH of 4.00. According to Zulkarnain (2013), mustard can grow well in soil with a pH between 6 -7. Subandi (2007) states soils with low pH is associated with high Al, Fe, and Mn concentrations, which can be toxic to plants. Aluminum toxicity will inhibit their root development, interfering with shoot growth (Yunita, 2009). Although soil pH does not directly affect N availability, it does impact soil microbial activity. Microbial activity is lower in acidic environments. Furthermore, low pH delays the N mineralization process from organic matter as well as the

nitrification process (Karyanto et al., 2012). Hence, low soil pH is one of the variables influencing low yields and decreased productivity of mustard greens. Consequently, adding synthetic alone is unlikely to increase yields of mustard greens in Ultisols; therefore, increasing the soil pH is necessary. The application of organic fertilizer on acid soil will increase its pH. A study by Hasanudin et al. (2021) confirmed that vermicompost and biourine increased pH of the Ultisols and vermicompost treatment significantly lowered the acidity of both Pb and Cd contaminated soils (Muktamar et al. 2021). Yustianingrum et al. (2022) reported that the application of compost increases organic-C, total soil-N, and soil pH.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research findings, the combination of 50% cow manure + 50% nitrogen and 75% cow manure + 25% nitrogen provide the highest mustard greens growth in Ultisols. This finding supports the implementation of sustainable agriculture using less synthetic fertilizer.

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